

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 11

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Iqtisodiyotning pul mablag'lari bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	16
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Yusupov Muxammadali Soxib o'g'li	
Driving economic growth through service exports.....	20
Rahimov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida jamoat tashkilotlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda jahon tajribasi.....	27
Raxmonov Abduxalil Rasulovich	
Raqamli marketing va mijozlar bilan ishlashning yangi usullari.....	31
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
Soliq tushumlarini shakllantirish ko'rsatkichlari asosida soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari	35
Jo'raev Husan	
Bevosita soliqqa tortish darajasini ko'paytirish omillari.....	41
Qodirov Baxodir Qudratovich	
Tijorat banklarining xo'jalik subyektlari bilan amalga oshiriladigan muddatli valyuta operatsiyalarini rivojlantirish	47
Ibodullaeva Ma'rifat To'liqin qizi	
Tovarlarning monopol yuqori (past) narxlarini aniqlashni takomillashtirish masalalari	52
Mingboev Asqar Qandaharovich	
Bojxona faoliyatini transformatsiyalashda innovatsion boshqaruvni takomillashtirishga oid xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Ro'ziboyev Muhiddin Xushnudovich	
Harnessing foreign direct investment for sustainable economic growth in Central Asia: policy challenges and opportunities.....	63
Mukhammedova Azizakhon Ikromjon kizi	
Mintaqa innovatsion faoliyatida tavakkalchilikni boshqarishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	68
Sapayeva N.K.	
Examining Uzbekistan's foreign trade indicators	72
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
Yo'l bo'yidagi xizmat ko'rsatish infratuzilmasini baholash: xizmat sifati va transport xavfsizligini oshirish.....	78
Egamberduyev Odil Buriboyevich	
Роль инноваций в гибком управлении проектами.....	82
Касимова Наима Жахангировна	
Sug'urta bozorini tartibga solishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	87
Tursunova Maftuna Agzamovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda madaniy turizm resurslarining o'rni va roli	91
Ro'zmetov Baxodir Shomurotovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining kapital bozorida emission faolligini oshirishning iqtisodiy asoslari	97
Shodmonova Munisa Nizamjon qizi	
Korxonaning tashqi bozorga chiqishida marketing strategiyasining samaradorligini baholash.....	104
Akramov Bo'ribek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatini boshqarish	110
Saipova Dilnoza Shuxratovna	

Xalqaro standartlar asosida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	114
Egamberdieva Salima Rayimovna, Bozorov Yashnarbek Xayrulla o'g'li	
Investitsiyalar samaradorligini baholash va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	120
Jo'raev Paxlavonjon Usarovich	
Soliq qarzdorliklarini yuzaga kelishining ilmiy nazariy asoslari tadqiqi	127
Ostonaqulov Alisher Abdurashidovich	
Korxonalarni moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularga imtiyozlar berishni takomillashtirish masalalari.....	132
Z.T. Mirzayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida korxonalarda raqamli marketingning ahamiyati.....	139
M.Vohobjonova	
Положение электронной коммерции на международном и национальном уровнях	142
Абдуганиев Учкун Хабибулла угли, Орифбоев Озод Азатович	
Korporativ resurslardan samarali foydalanish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarini barqaror rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirish.....	148
Jalolova Muazzamxon Akbarjonovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida kartoshka ishlab chiqarish funksiyasi.....	151
Avazmurodov Islom Nusratullo o'g'li, Muratov Shukrullo Abduraimovich	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati bo'yicha logistik muammolar va ularni bartaraf etishning samarali yechimlari	155
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev	
Ta'lim va ilm-fan sohasida inson kapitali konsepsiyasining amalga oshish bosqichlari yo'nalishlari.....	159
Nasretdinova Aziza Adxamjonovna , Bozarov Elyor Boboqulovich	
Влияние цифровой валюты центральных банков (CBDC) на международную торговлю и финансовые отношения: Анализ и перспективы	164
Номозали Хайдаров	
Raqamli transformatsiya va tadbirkorlik: kichik biznes uchun yangi imkoniyatlar va chora-tadbirlar	167
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich, TDIU magistranti	
O'zbekiston respublikasida aholini samarali ish bilan ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	172
Raxmatullayeva Shahnoza Xamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchxon Sadriddin qizi	
Aylanma mablag'lar aylanuvchanligini tezlashtirishning asosiy yo'llari	179
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Mintaqada to'qimachilik sanoatining iqtisodiy holati tahlili (Xorazm viloyati misolida)	185
Xudoyorova M.O	
Мировой опыт стратегического управления финансовыми ресурсами акционерных обществ.....	190
Абдалиев Айдос Бахтиярович	
Sug'urta faoliyatida axborot jarayonlarini vtomatlashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	196
Shakirov O'tkirbek Taxirovich	
Yerlardan maqsadli foydalanishni aniqlash uslubi.....	199
Yunusov Begench Mavlanberdievich	
Iqtisodiyotda real sektorning ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi.....	204
Amirqulov Umarali Akram o'g'li	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni baholash amaliyoti va indikatorlari	208
Feruz Raxmatova Yusupjanovna	
O'zbekistonda korxonalarni boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan qo'llash yo'nalishlari	213
Qo'chqorov Tohir Safarovich, To'ychiyev Akmaljon Abdulatif o'g'li	

Agroklasterning tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati	219
Qurbonov Alisher Boboqulovich	
“Yashil” Iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda turizmga investitsiyalarning roli	224
Azimov Olimjon Orifovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalar asosida aholini ro‘yxatga olish jarayonlarini samarali tashkil etish	236
Annazarova Barno Rustamovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligida sug‘oriladigan yerlar unumdorligini oshirishni iqtisodiy rag‘batlantirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	242
Isaxanov Muslimjon Ma‘rifjon o‘g‘li	
Logistika va uning sanoat mahsulot ishlab chiqarish tannarxiga ta‘sirini kamaytirish	246
Zokirjonov Asadbek Otabek o‘g‘li	
Sug‘urta kampaniyalari moliyaviy risklarini baholash	249
Baymuratova Gulirayxon Tursunbaevna	
Tadbirkorlik salohiyati tushunchasining rivojlanish bosqichlari	255
Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o‘g‘li	
Qishloqlarning resurs salohiyati iqtisodiy kategoriya va iqtisodiyotning agrar sektorini rivojlantirishning zaruriy sharti sifatida	260
Tursunpo‘latov Farxodjon Xoshimjon o‘g‘li	
Kommunal xizmatlarni rivojlantirishda xorij tajribasidan foydalanish.....	265
Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi	
Analysis of factors affecting the sustainable development of transport networks in Khorezm	269
Karimboev Dilshod Davronbek o‘g‘li	
Tijorat banklari moliyaviy boshqaruv tizimini tashkiliy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	274
Lutfullo Xalimovich Qadirov	
Использование социальных сетей как инструмента маркетинга для фермеров	278
Назарова Гулрух Умаржоновна	
O‘zbekiston transport-logistika tizimida logistika samaradorligi indeksi (LPI) va uning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatidagi ahamiyati	283
Ismoilov Narimonjon No‘monjon o‘g‘li	
Davlat maqsadli dasturlarini imtiyozli kreditlash tizimining mamlakat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi o‘rni.....	287
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekistonda potensial YaIM.ning ekonometrik tahlili	293
Djabbarov Raximjon Abdullaevich	
Tibbiyot muassasalarini kafolatlangan tibbiy xizmatlar paketi asosida moliyalashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish masalalari	298
Muxammadiev Ramz Zoirjon o‘g‘li	
Стратегии развития медицинских организаций в Узбекистане	313
Исломбек Умиров	
Kambag‘allikka qarshi kurashning falsafiy va ijtimoiy asoslari: Tarixiy tahlil	321
Iloxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o‘g‘li	
Innovatsion loyihalar va startaplarni moliyalashtirishda venchur fondlarining ahamiyati.....	329
Atamuradov Sherzod Akramovich	
Reforms in higher education institutions of the republic of uzbekistan	334
Gafurov Anvar Bazarbayevich	
Namangan viloyati qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining faoliyati samaradorligini ta‘minlash holati va tahlili	343
Ibrogimov Sherzodbek Xalimjon o‘g‘li	

Increasing the innovation potential of construction materials industry enterprises.....	350
Kurbanova Shaxnoza Yuldashbayevna	
Jahon savdo tashkiloti doirasida to'qimachilik mahsulotlarining xalqaro savdosi.....	356
Nurbojev Jaloliddin Mamadiyevich, Abduvohidov Behzod	
Farg'ona vodiysida turizm xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlili.....	361
Mamatqulov Zarifbek Sharifjonovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari.....	366
Ko'chqarov Fayzullo Abdujabborovich	
Tarkibiy o'zgarishlar sharoitlarida xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda investitsiyalarni faollashtirish.....	376
M.J.Nabiyeva	
O'zbekistonda aholi omonatlari va ularni kafolatlash tizimi.....	382
Xakimov Zohid Norbo'tayevich	
Взаимодействие образования и бизнеса с элементами дуального образования.....	389
Баходурова Сулхия Азизхожаевна, Акрамова Зарринахон Башировна, Ли Марина Рудольфовна, Ромашкин Роман Анатольевич, Мухтарова Доната Равшанбековна	
O'zbekistonda yashirin iqtisodiyot darajasini qisqartirishda samarali yondoshuv.....	396
Bobojonov Azimjon Akmal o'g'li	
To'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyalarini takomillashtirish zaruriyati.....	403
Sarimsaqov Doniyor Xomidovich	
Xorazm viloyatida hududiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish darajasini baholash.....	409
Madraximov Kaxramon Egamberganovich	
O'zbekistonda aholini uy-joy bilan ta'minlashdagi murakkabliklar va ularning yechimlari.....	414
Xannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
Elektron hukumatdan smart hukumatga.....	419
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznesni rivojlanishi va samaradorligining nazariy-uslubiy asoslar.....	426
Axatova Shaxnoza	
O'zbekistonda banklar faoliyatini tartibga solishning zamonaviy mexanizmlari.....	432
Abdullaev Suyun Artikovich	
Raqamli transformatsiya va hududlarning inklyuziv iqtisodiy o'sishini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	436
Zokirova Bahora Zokir qizi	
Market research strategies in the global tech industry: a comparative study of apple, samsung, and huawei.....	440
Abbos Ruzmamatov	
Strategic analysis of innovation development in manufacturing enterprises: approaches, challenges, and future perspectives.....	444
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda moliyalashtirish texnologiyasi.....	452
Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich	
Boshqarish jarayonlarini samaradorligini oshirish orqali iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni ta'minlash.....	459
Xo'jamurodov Asqarjon Jalolovich, Usmonov Suxrob Zayniddin o'gli	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni: amalga oshirish imkoniyatlari va kelajak istiqbollari.....	469
Kurbanov Farrux Uktamovich	
Kichik biznes uchun investitsion muhit jozibadorligining ko'rsatkichlari tahlili.....	469
Jurayev Elyorbek Sobirjon o'g'li, Nabiyeva Muhabbat Djabirxanovna	

Fiskal va monetar siyosatni muvofiqlashtirishda inflyatsiya ko'rsatkichining ekonometrik tahlili	475
Hakimov Hakimjon Abdullo o'g'li	
Bandlikni ta'minlashning moliyaviy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	479
Karimjonov Muhammadrasul To'liqinjon o'g'li	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
O'zbekiston mintaqalarida turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarishda davlat-xususiy sherikligi mexanizmidan foydalanishning konseptual modelini ishlab chiqish	485
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon Begmatovna	
Аутсорсинг и рост сферы услуг: воздействие на занятость (практика США)	494
Назаров Зиёвуддин Шарофиддинович	
Restoran xizmatlari sohasi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda marketingning zamonaviy konsepsiyalarini qo'llash	501
Ibodov Kamoliddin Mamatqulovich	
The revenue manager in the hospitality industry	507
Kalandarova Gulnoza	
Davlat moliyaviy nazoratini joriy etilishi bo'yicha ayrim xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari	510
B.Turabov	
Barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlashning hududiy xususiyatlari.....	517
Baxtiyorova Dildora	
Elektr energiyasi samaradorligini yaxshilashga innovatsion va strategik yondashuvlar.....	521
Doliyev Shoxabbos Qulmurot o'g'li	
Don maxsulotlari sifat ko'rsatkichlariga sovuq konditsionerlash tizimini samaradorligini tahlil qilish	525
Yusupov Azamat Alijonovich, Akramova Gulhayo Abidovna	
O'zbekistonda tijorat banklarini rivojlantirish va transformatsiya qilish istiqbollari	532
Mutalova Mohira	
Optimizing crisis-handling mechanisms in commercial banks	537
Muydinov Muhammadsardor Abdukayum ugli	
Ochiq bank (open banking) faoliyatining xalqaro tajribasi va o'zbekistonda qo'llanilishi	541
Xoshimov Elmurod Abdusattorovich, Abduvahobov Shohruh Xolmo'min o'g'li	
Mikrosug'urtaning kichik biznes risklarini sug'urtalashning innovatsion mexanizmi sifatidagi ahamiyati.....	549
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
Agroklastarlarni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashning iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	553
Topildiev Soxibjon Raximjonovich, Nasirxodjayeva Dilafruz Sabitxanovna	
Econometric analysis and adjustment of agricultural production processes.....	563
Makhambetova Uringul	
The importance of investing investment in fixed capital.....	568
Sindarov Sherzod Egamberdiyevich, Ruzimatov Sanjarbek Qosimjon ugli	
Kichik biznes iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda kasanachilik va mahalliy yetkazib beruvchilarni rivojlantirish	573
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari bozorining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	577
Zaidov Islom Ibragimjonovich	
Respublika iqtisodiyotining innovatsion salohiyati va undan foydalanish.....	583
Olchinboyev Otabek Abdusamad o'g'li	

Математическое моделирование забойки при использовании вв с экспоненциальным внешнем воздействием	587
Джуроева Нодира Мурадуллаевна	
Kichik biznes subyektlari faoliyatini moliyaviy ta'minoti masalalari	593
Aymurzaeva Gulnaz Puxarbaevna	
Logistika harajatlarini optimallashtirish shartlari.....	598
N.B. Shanazarova	
G'ozaning yangi tizmalari tolasining sifat ko'rsatkichlari	603
X.A.Boltabaev, X.A.Mamadjonov	
Aholi turmush darajasi baholashda daromadlarning ahamiyati	607
Tursunov Farxod Baxodir o'g'li, Qambarov Bahriddin Panji o'g'li	
Xodimlar bilan hisob-kitoblar hisobining nazariy va normativ-huquqiy asoslari.....	618
Ametova Nasiba Danilovna	
Nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlar boshqaruvida zaifliklar	622
Odilbekova Dilnoza Murataliyevna	
Respublika iqtisodiyotida oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlanish tendensiyalari	626
Baxritdinov Sherzodbek Bahodirovich	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning xorijiy ilg'or davlatlar tajribasi.....	631
Qaxxorov Shoxruxbek Shavkatjon o'g'li	
Порядок аудита лизинговых операций	636
Турсунов Улугбек Сативолдиевич	
Fond bozorida aksiyalar muomalasi tahlili.....	641
Quvondiqov Muhammad Quvondiqovich	
Низкоуглеродное развитие: ключевой фактор устойчивого развития в узбекистане и мировом контексте	646
Исламов Шохзод Шухрат ўғли	
Устойчивое управление ресурсами: роль государственного управления, квоты на природные ресурсы и производительности энергии.....	653
Ибрагимов Захид Тахирович	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda sanoat korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash va rivojlantirish usullari.....	661
Yuldashev Fozil Turapovich	
Food security problems.....	667
Shukurov Tohirjon Izzatullo o'g'li	
Waste management in the dairy industry	669
Shukurov Izzatullo Khikmatullaevich	
Sanoat korxonalariga kiritilgan investitsiyalar samaradorligining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	675
Feruzha Hojiqulova Dona qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini eksport salohiyatini oshirishda vujudga kelayotgan muammolar va ularning yechimlari	683
Yuldasheva Dildora Kamiljan qizi	
O'zbekistonda budjet tashkilotlarida moliyaviy nazoratini olib borishning ustuvor yo'llari	687
Alxanova Feruzha Faxritdinovna	
O'zbekistonda davlat xaridlari tizimini takomillashtirish.....	691
Shermatov G'ofurjon G'ulamovich, Mamasoliev Abrorbek Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Kichik tadbirkorlik tarkibiy tuzilmasi takomillashuvida tarmoq bo'yicha ixtisoslashuv jarayonlarining ahamiyati va ularning rivojlanganlik darajasiga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillar	696
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	

Raqamli platformalar orqali yashil mahsulotlar va xizmatlarni rivojlantirish	709
Nurmetova Muyassar Jumanazarovna	
Development and practical application of financial security indicators at the regional level: The case of Uzbekistan	715
Elmurodov Shohzod Shavkatovich	
Boshqaruv psixologiyasining terminologik tahlili va semantik xususiyatlari	720
Norboyeva Dilafruza Jumaqulovna	
Mintaqa ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga kiritilgan investitsiyalarning iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili	724
Tursunpulat Davronovich Maxmudov	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlar mahsulotlar eksportini motivatsiyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish	730
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish huquqiy kafolatlari	735
Usmonov Shavkatjon Shukurovich	
Nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyatini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashning amaliy jihatlari	744
Muslitdinov Nodir Xojievich	
Korxonalarda qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini joriy etish sharoitida strategik loyixa boshqaruvi	750
Orifali Samandarovich Tursunov, Xalilov Jaxangir Jalolovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro fond bozori holati tahlili	756
Shamsiev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarini innovasion faoliyatini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash yo'llari	764
Shaniyazova Zamira Oralbaevna	
Raqamli transformasiya jarayonlarining bank xizmatlari sifati va xavfsizligini oshirishga ta'siri	772
Qodirov Bekzod Xushnud o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari ipoteka xizmatini raqamlashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	776
Jabbarov Majidbek Erzodovich	
Fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyati samaradorligini statistik usullarda baholash	780
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
Sanoat korxonalarida moliyaviy barqarorlik, ularni hisoblash va oshirish yo'llari	784
Makhkamova Shakhruza Bahodir qizi	
O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlik salohiyatini rivojlantirish borasida amalga oshirilayotgan chora-tadbirlar	788
G'ofurjon Shermatov G'ulamovich, Baxtiyor Xabibullayev Abdulvoxid o'g'li	
Tannarxni pasaytirishda ish vaqtdan samarali foydalanish va mehnat sig'imi tahlili	794
Xamidova S.Ya.	
Umumta'lim muassasalari xarajatlarini moliyalashtirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish	799
Ummatov Avaz Muydinovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'idagi tarkibiy-tuzilmaviy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash	803
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
Measures for the development of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan	813
Khallieva Nargiza Rozikovna	
Turizm raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash bo'yicha jaxon tajribasi	820
Jalolov Otabek Oybek o'g'li	

Формирование страхового бизнеса как стратегического сектора экономики.....	826
Тулаев Дилшод Юсуфович	
Особенности использования инструментов монетарной политики в зарубежных странах.....	831
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
Некоторые аспекты технологического развития в современной экономике.....	839
Ахмедов К.	
Формирование конкурентоспособных профессионалов для рынка.....	842
Ишимбаев Рафаэль Наильевич	
Влияние инвестиций на оценку эффективности использования интеллектуального капитала.....	848
Муртазаев Ардашер Зафар угли	
Navoiy viloyatida kichik biznes faoliyatini rivojlantirish holatini statistik bashorat qilish.....	853
Xushvaqova Durdonal Islom qizi	
Foreign trade liberalization and its impact on a country's economic growth (in the case of countries).....	860
Sirajiddinov Nishanbay, Norkobilov Akobir	
Samarqand viloyati xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	871
Umirov Islombek Furkatovich, Ozodxonov Islombek Zarifxon o'g'li, Turaqulov Ulug'bek Shovkat o'g'li	
O'zbekistonning jahon savdo tashkilotiga qoshilishi natijasida xom ashyolar importining yengillashishi va mahsulotga ketadigan xarajatlarning kamayishi masalalari.....	880
Z.K. Xashimova	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarining samaradorligini ekonometrik modellashtirish.....	885
Musurmonova Mahbuba Omonovna	
Yuqori malakali kadrlar tayyorlash samaradorligi iqtisodiy-statistik tahlili.....	892
Zaripova Mukaddas Djumayozovna	
Xususiy kredit – kreditning zamonaviy turi sifatida.....	902
Sharbat Abdullaeva, Abdullaev Sardor Atxam o'g'li	
Jahon iqtisodiyotida yuzaga kelgan megatrendlarning o'zbekistonning tashqi savdo munosabatlariga ta'siri.....	907
Yangibaeva Dilafruz Polat qizi	
Issues of reflection of financial results in reports and improvement of audit.....	912
Muhammedova Dilfuza Anvarovna, Shukurov Farrux Shuxrat o'g'li	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlar mahsulotlar eksportini motivatsiyalash mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	918
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Mamlakatimizda uy xo'jaliklari iqtisodiy faolligini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	918
Abdullayev S.A.	
Etnografik turizm samaradorligini oshirishda xorij tajribasini qo'llash.....	922
Xakimov Dilyor Zafarovich	
Davlat muassasalarida inson resurslaridan foydalanish samaradorligining statistik tadqiqi.....	930
Xusanova Muxsina Kasimovna	
Raqamli marketing va barqaror strategiyalar orqali mintaqaviy investitsiyaviy jozibadorlikni oshirish: AHP asosidagi tahlil.....	937
Xolmurotova Diyoraxon Ibragimovna	
Sanoat korxonalarida iqtisodiy salohiyatni rivojlantirishda qo'laniladigan strategiyalar.....	943
Turaboyev Ibroxim Ismoil o'g'li	
Innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishi.....	948
Maxmudov Abrorxon Axmadxonovich	

Issues of strategic planning in industrial enterprises.....	952
Ibragimov Isroil Usmanovich	
Sanoat korxonalarida tejamkor texnologiyalarni joriy qilishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	958
Xakimov Umarxon Rustamjon o'g'li	
Цифровая экономика: концептуальные основы и ее влияние на трансформация рынка труда.....	962
Магруппов Азиз Юлдашевич	
Taraqqiyot strategiyasi va ma'muriy islohotlarning keyingi bosqichlari.....	971
Abdulla Abdukadirov	
Экономический эффект от внедрения международных образовательных стандартов в узбекистане.....	977
Олимова Бахора Шухратовна	
Ijtimoiy xizmatlat sohasini rivojlanish tendentsiyalari va davlat-xususiy sherikligini samarali shakllantirish mexanizmlari	981
Y.M.Xalikov	
Qurilish materiallari ishlab chiqarilishida kimyo sanoatining o'rni.....	988
Usmanov Baxtiyor Xusanboyevich	
Hududiy sanoatni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati va uning salohiyatini belgilovchi omillar	994
Choriyev Tolib A'zamovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida banklar faoliyatini innovatsion rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	999
Qosimova Mohigul Abduhamidovna	
Tasvirlarni intellektuallashtirishda filtrlash jarayoni va baholash algoritmlari	1004
Norboyeva Nafisa	
Model of application of the integrated report on the organisation's human capital in management accounting	1009
Ochilov Olmos Ikrom ugli	

MODEL OF APPLICATION OF THE INTEGRATED REPORT ON THE ORGANISATION'S HUMAN CAPITAL IN MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING

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Abstract: The article reveals the necessity, significance, goals and objectives, as well as practical aspects of compiling an integrated report on human capital used for management accounting purposes in economic entities. The analysis of approaches to disclosing information about human capital in financial statements and the scientific and methodological foundations of reporting on integration, including both financial and non-financial indicators for management purposes, are highlighted. Important analytical indicators reflecting human capital also have been suggested in this report.

Key words: human capital, accounting, financial statements, integrated reporting, management accounting, financial indicators, non-financial indicators.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda boshqaruv hisobi maqsadlarida qo'llaniladigan inson kapitali to'g'risida integratsiyalashgan hisobotni tuzishning zarurati, ahamiyati, maqsad va vazifalari hamda amaliy jihatlari ochib berilgan. Inson kapitaliga oid axborotlarning moliyaviy hisobotlarda ochib berilishiga oid yondashuvlar tahlili hamda boshqaruv maqsadlarida ham moliyaviy ham nomoliyaviy ko'rsatkichlarni o'z ichiga oluvchi integratsiyalashga hisobot tuzishning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur hisobotda inson kapitalini ifodalovchi muhim tahliliy ko'rsatkichlar ham taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: inson kapitali, buxgalteriya hisobi, moliyaviy hisobot, integratsiyalashgan hisobot, boshqaruv hisobi, moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar, nomoliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar.

Аннотация: В статье раскрываются необходимость, значение, цели и задачи, а также практические аспекты составления интегрированного отчета о человеческом капитале, используемого в целях управленческого учета в хозяйствующих субъектах. Освещены анализ подходов к раскрытию информации о человеческом капитале в финансовой отчетности и научно-методические основы составления отчетности на интеграцию, включающей как финансовые, так и нефинансовые показатели в целях управления. В данном отчете также предложены важные аналитические показатели, отражающие человеческий капитал.

Ключевые слова: человеческий капитал, бухгалтерский учет, финансовая отчетность, интегрированная отчетность, управленческий учет, финансовые показатели, нефинансовые показатели.

INTRODUCTION

At present, an individual with his or her education, qualifications and experience is an important reserve that stimulates the development of an organisation, and effective investment in human capital contributes to the achievement of strategically important goals in the shortest possible time. Moreover, while a specific approach to the disclosure of data on common resources has already been developed in reporting, such an approach is only at the beginning of its development in relation to human capital.

Professor E. Flamholtz believes that reporting on human resources should be designed to improve the quality of financial decisions by informing internal and external users about human resources [1, p.1-5].

By using monetary measures, particularly cost, profit and value, it becomes possible to fulfil the three main functions of human resource accounting:

- 1) to provide information about the value and importance of people as organisational resources;
- 2) to provide a basis for facilitating decision making;
- 3) motivate managers and investors to recognise the human resource accounting perspective.

At present, financial statements are unable to measure and show the most significant business factors, which are human, organisational and customer capital. Financial statements cannot communicate to managers, society, investors about the role of human resources in the future revenue growth of the organisation.

In the current economic conditions for the purposes of formation and disclosure of information on personnel costs, on the basis of the methods and approaches considered, we can conclude that despite the emerging difficulties with recognition as an independent type of long-term assets, identification and objective cost estimation in monetary terms of investments in human resources of the organisation, it is impossible to identify any one universal model of formation of information on various aspects of the organisation's activities. Each approach is individual and requires fine-tuning for the current financial and economic activity of the entity.

Based on the above, it should be noted that improving the system of accounting and reporting on human capital information is one of the important topics of scientific research today. Effective management of internal and external information is achieved by providing users with important information about the company's human capital. As a result, in a competitive environment, business entities will be able to maintain their positions in the market and achieve their goals, ensuring their sustainable development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human capital should not only be developed but also preserved. For this purpose, it is advisable to constantly create additional investments in its formation and establishment, as well as to ensure an efficient system of human capital management. As a consequence, in the conditions of the digital economy, the formation and development of a methodology for the integrated assessment of human capital, as well as the display of human capital in the reporting of organisations, is an urgent task that has a scientific and practical content. In order to implement the process of preparation and development of integrated reporting on human capital, it is advisable to improve approaches to the display of data on the organisation's activities in the accounting and information system [2].

When considering the points of view of American researchers S.A. Dipiazza and R.J. Eccles, a single report is a document that includes financial and non-financial data on the work of the organisation [3].

According to T. Lessidrenska, Director of the Business Ethics Programme, who is a commissioner of the Global Reporting Initiative, an integrated report is primarily a management report, considered as a practical basis for managing an organisation [4].

Professor S.F. Legenchuk emphasised such unified directions of the formation of accounting and reporting [5]:

In accounting:

- The use of accounting data to guarantee the approval of effective management decisions;
- increase in the composition of accounting objects;
- smooth transition to fair value estimates and forecast values from historical estimates;

in reporting:

- development of financial reporting orientation for general use;
- the need to supply data: prospective and forecasting; non-financial data on important value-forming factors for the organisation; financial and non-financial data on the social and environmental functioning of the organisation; on the objects of a highly productive economy.

There is controversy among scholars because of the types of capital that must necessarily be analysed in reporting. For example, economists O.V. Plotnikova and V.S. Plotnikov, N.V. Malinovskaya, M.A. Vakhrushina, O.V. Efimova, L.N. Gerasimova, S.A. Samusenko agree with the need to disclose information on 6 types of capital in integrated reporting [6,7,8,9].

The considered concepts of integrated reporting, which complement rather than contradict each other, allowed us to outline our author's definition: "Integrated reporting is a modern approach that represents a new stage in the development of accounting and the latest way to inform shareholders about the financial position and performance of the organisation, including not only financial but also non-financial data" [10].

METHODOLOGY

This study employed general scientific methods and techniques to reveal the integrated reporting on human capital for management accounting purposes and its application. In particular, methods such as analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, monographic observation, systematization, comparison and grouping were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The limited disclosure of human capital in the financial statements accompanied the development of separate versions of data representation about this resource in accounting and reporting systems. Among the variety of versions of presentation of information on human capital in financial statements, we will emphasise such approaches in Table 1.

Table 1. Approaches on the reflection of human capital in financial statements.

Approach.	Disadvantages	Commentary
1. Show human capital in the balance sheet under the item «Investments in human capital»	As an asset, inconsistency in the recognition criteria. Difficulties in determining useful life	Human capital is an asset, investments in human capital are capitalised
2. Show human capital under «Goodwill» in the balance sheet and disclosure of human capital in the financial statements	Internally generated goodwill is not recognised as an asset because it is very difficult to identify and measure reliably	When buying a business, the organisation that buys the business pays not only for the assets that are shown on the organisation's books but also pays for specially trained employees
3. In the financial statements, disclosure of human capital in current expenses	This option of accounting for human capital is appropriate only for organisations with a small share of human resource costs	
4. Show human capital as a liability on the liability side of the balance sheet	To the same extent as in the previous approach, human capital is captured indirectly and data on human capital are lacking	It is recommended to form a fund «Financial liabilities for payments to human capital» from retained earnings

At the same time, employee data may be disclosed in non-financial statements. In accordance with IFRS 1 Presentation of Financial Statements, an entity may disclose additional data that accompanies the financial statements, provided that the executive body perceives it to be of value to stakeholders when approving economic decisions. These additional data at the current stage of development may be human capital data [11].

For example, to disclose human capital data, the Institute for Human Capital Management, which provides services in the field of human capital management analytics and value forecasting, has produced three reports known to us as human capital reports. These reports consist of [12]:

- human capital balance sheet - this report helps to quantify the importance of human resources as well as calculate the value of human capital by employee category;
- report on the movement of human capital provides data on the movement of human resources divided by the duration of time, analysing the situation where and how human capital is placed and applied;
- report on the impact of human capital on financial results - the report provides a quantitative assessment of the way in which human capital has an impact on financial values.

It should be emphasised that reporting information on human capital is of great value, because in a given period, investment in human capital has a significant share in total capital investment. So if the data on assets and liabilities, which are shown in the financial statements of the organisation, are accessible to users and can be subject to analysis, then the quality of data on human capital and its management strategy, which are subject to disclosure in the statements and contribute to the users in assessing the performance of such investments, in the present period has no specific regulation and requires more detailed research. Therefore, there are proposals from modern scientists to form internal financial reporting for management personnel, which is based on the grouping of expenditure items on the formation, reproduction and use of human capital at the level of the organisation for the purpose of its effective management.

In accounting science there are rather fundamental rules and principles, dependence between objects, which during centuries appear unchanged, but accounting science would have no possibility for development, if new approaches and new directions would not appear in science, which would contribute to the approach of accounting and reporting data, first, to the degree of development of society, economy, advanced information technologies and, second, not to contradict the information demand of users. Regularly created accounting innovations - from minor to global, very often do not contain a long-term character or concern a small number of organisations. But some innovations in accounting science become widely popularised and, existing for quite a long period of time, jointly create a new stage of its formation, most likely a new model.

The study of the directions of formation of financial reporting is associated with the problem - the difficulty of studying financial reporting separately from other types of accounting and reporting, not only from financial accounting. At the current stage of formation of information support of the economy all types of information, technologies and methodologies of its development correlate with each other.

One of the key documents that regulates the reflection of human capital data in reporting is the standard on integrated reporting, which was created in 2013 by the International Integrated Reporting Council. This standard defines all principles, concepts, recommendations and requirements for the preparation of an integrated report.

The need for integrated reporting can be described by the fact that investors insist on more and more disclosure of data about different aspects of an organisation's performance. Investors are interested not only in data on the financial position of the organisation and its performance, which are reflected in the financial statements, but also in data on economic and social factors. Providing users with integrated reporting in a highly competitive environment is an effective means of enhancing an organisation's reputation and investment merit.

As a result, integrated reporting will help organisations make the most motivated decisions in terms of sustainability goals, and contributors and other investors will gain more meaningful insights into their performance. Such actions require the design and development of a new reporting framework that combines the requirements that can be used in traditional financial reporting, including the best strategies for integrated reporting.

As far as human capital is concerned, when creating integrated reporting, the organisation is obliged to outline its policies specifically in the field of human resources management, in addition to offering an analysis of how the strategic objectives in this field are being achieved. Meanwhile, today there is no clear regulation of the form in which information on human capital should be presented in integrated reporting, as well as what indicators of the efficiency of the strategy of managing this resource are optimal.

In contrast to financial reporting, integrated reporting includes aggregated data on the organisation's human capital. It necessarily takes into account the strategic objectives, which makes it possible to forecast the organisation's development, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparative characteristics of integrated and financial reporting.

Criterion	Integrated reporting	Financial statements
Composition of information	Includes information data not only on financial performance but also on external actions	Covers data on assets, liabilities, financial results and cash flows
Capital	Includes data on six types of capital (financial, industrial, human, intellectual, etc.)	Includes information data on financial capital only
Interrelationship of information	Interdependent information	Scattered data and interpretations of the manual
Reporting perimeter	Subject to risks, opportunities and outcomes that have a significant impact on the organisation's ability to create value	Subject to the reporting standards that govern the concept of control
Accuracy of reporting elements	More accurately accounts for the organisation's resources as well as the organisation's performance	The individual elements of the report are not accurately and limitedly shown
Adaptability	High, ability to respond to circumstances	Low, specific adherence to rules
Time period	Short-, medium- and long-term	Short-term
Forecasting capability	Aiming for future periods, the filling is carried out with necessary consideration of all types of risks and strategic goals of the organisation	Focusing on past performance does not allow you to predict the future of the organisation
Transparency	High transparency because it reflects more information about the implementation of the organisation's work	Low transparency because a small amount of performance information is reflected
Regulation	Not regulated by IFRS	Regulated by legislation and IFRS

The first fundamental concept of integrated reporting is the concept of multiple capitals, i.e. that capitals are the sources of value and resources in an organisation's business model.

The second fundamental concept is the business model, which is at the heart of integrated reporting. An organisation's business model is its chosen structure of resources, ways of doing business, results and products, which is designed to create value in the short, medium and long term and can be seen as the fundamental activities of the organisation.

The third fundamental concept of integrated reporting is 'value creation'. Integrated reporting shows how an organisation creates value by increasing, decreasing or changing the amount of capital associated with the organisation's activities. In contrast to traditional reporting, integrated reporting reflects the broadest range of value creation relationships. At the same time, it should provide stakeholders not only with the necessary data, but also with a holistic picture of the interdependence and interconnectedness of different types of capital (Table 3).

Table 3. Types of capital used in the organization.

Type of capital	Definition of capital
Production	Physical facilities that organisations can use to produce goods and services
Financial	Own and borrowed funds of the organisation used for production of goods and services
Human	The skills and experience of individuals and their receptivity to innovation. Components: - Agreement and facilitation of the organisation's management of ethical values (e.g. recognition of people's rights); - skill in understanding and implementing the organisation's strategy; - support and incentive for quality improvement, capacity for co-operation and leadership
Social	Institutions and relationships within and between communities, shareholder groups and other relationships. Components: - shared values, behaviours; - The basic relationships, trust, and support that the organisation builds and strives to maintain with partners and customers; - The organisation's licence to operate
Intelligent	Intangible assets that create competitive advantage: reputation, brand and intellectual property itself (copyright, patents, software, etc.)
Natural	Committed resources for the production of goods, provision of services, and the organisation's impact on the environment. Includes: - land, water, resources, minerals, forests; - Ecosystem health and biodiversity

Integrated reporting is designed to solve such problems: reporting that reflects not only financial but also non-financial data in a concise and user-friendly form. The main purpose of integrated reporting is to form a universal and common concept of corporate reporting, which is created in relation to the business model itself, to the strategic goals and management standards of the organisation.

Another important component of the report is the concept of integrated thinking. According to ICIE, the development of such a mindset will contribute to the financial stability and sustainable development of the company, as such a mindset is aimed at the efficient and productive allocation of capital. Moreover, the very implementation of integrated reporting in a company requires from the company's management a leadership type of behaviour that is based on social responsibility.

The analysis of various approaches of scientists to the definition of the essence of human capital and the effectiveness of its management allows us to conclude that the strategy of human capital management must be reflected in integrated reporting in the following areas:

- formation and establishment of the concept of strategic planning of the organisation in relation to human resources management. Alignment of this concept as a whole with the goals and objectives of the organisation;
- supplying the needs of the organisation with qualified specialists. Achievement of this goal is likely to be achieved both by increasing the percentage of graduates from secondary and higher specialised educational institutions and by preparing and implementing individual measures to attract and develop inexperienced personnel;

- development and maintenance of an efficient system of training and development of specialists. The organisation of this training system arises from planning the need for training, identifying the key aspects of training, in addition to getting the advantage to qualitatively evaluate the knowledge that has been obtained by employees. It is necessary to emphasise that the training system should be created in relation to the most important goals and development objectives of the organisation. On the issue of personnel evaluation: the results of evaluation are extremely important in determining the performance and productivity of specialists;

- establishment of an effective system of remuneration and reimbursement. Integrated reporting may include the following sections.

1. Consistent information about the organisation (types of activities, mission, development strategy, performance indicators, etc.).

2. environmental information: data on people, facts, objects, events, processes and phenomena relevant to environmental protection, ensuring environmental safety, protecting public health and other data, regardless of the form in which they are provided, explaining the environmental situation in localities.

3. Social information: expenditure on the formation and development of human capital; dynamics of hiring and dismissal of employees; expenditure on social packages for employees; expenditure on support for schools, kindergartens and homes, etc. 4.

4. Innovation activities include expenditure on R&D, expenditure on the introduction of new technologies or the purchase of modern equipment.

5. The characterisation of the internal control system shows such main aspects:

- Control of the relevance and validity of the information provided in relation to its objective - the management should define the scope of duties of an individual employee responsible for the achievement of the set objectives, taking into account the schedule of work procedures;

- Assessing the quality of accounting information - performed by internal audit;

- Monitoring of compliance with planned values - creation of a system of normative data, identification of performers and reasons for non-compliance.

6. Records of reporting indicators - specification of individual reporting data and disclosure of categories not reflected in the composition of reporting data.

7. Analysis of the organisation's financial performance and financial position.

The characteristic structure and composition of the indicators is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Structure of Integrated Reporting Indicators.

The structure of the sections and their information value are related to the peculiarities of the organisation and the properties of the external economic environment, the purposeful instructions of the top management and other factors. Creation of integrated reporting is in the sphere of professional work of the organisation's management. Consequently, integrated reporting is a type of management reporting, and its content and composition depend not only on external and internal circumstances, but also on the direction of interest to the users of this accounting information (i.e. we are talking about external and internal integrated reporting).

The most important indicators of integrated reporting are classified according to such components [13, p.6]:

- economic component: revenues and retained earnings, payments to employees, suppliers of materials, raw materials, capital, the state;

- environmental component: results of work, which are combined with energy, water, raw materials inputs; environmental costs; waste emission and discharge operations;

- social component: number of employees and staff turnover, education and training, workplace safety, health, relations between management and employees, salary levels, etc.

The difficulty of reflecting information on human capital in integrated reporting is primarily due to the fact that this capital has fundamentally distinctive features. Thus, initially an individual owns his labour force, but when it is sold it turns out to be capital. However, this type of capital, in contrast to others, cannot be separated from the individual, but can only be rented for a specified fee. Thus, the knowledge, skills, qualifications of an individual are subject to rent for the employer in relation to the acquisition of income from human capital.

When creating integrated reporting in the part of human capital, the organisation is obliged to clearly define the policy in the field of human resources management, as well as to present an analysis of how exactly the strategic goal in this field is being achieved at the moment and what are the prospects for development in the future. Meanwhile, today there is no clear regulation in what form the data on human capital should be reflected in the integrated reporting, as well as what data of the effective strategy of human capital management will be the most favourable.

Because human capital, as well as other types of capital, is subject to certain types of risk, for example, the risk of payback, the risk of rationality of investments in human resources, the key task of each company is to create a human capital management strategy, in addition to the possibility of assessing the effectiveness of this strategy. At the present moment effective and productive strategy of human capital management is extremely important, because it contributes to determination of the most favourable need in human resources, forecasting of expenses for preservation and formation of human capital in short-term, medium-term and long-term periods. This fact is above all, because the overabundance of human resources often causes a decrease in the performance of the organisation and an increase in similar costs associated with employees. Along with this deficit of human capital is unfavourable for the work of the organisation, because in this case there is a deterioration in the quality of work.

The modern reporting model is designed to give a clear and concise vision of the quality of administrative resources in the organisation, showing, at the same time, its ability to recreate and maintain value at the present time and in the future period; to determine the degree of application and dependence on a variety of resources; the relationship of human, intellectual, financial, social, production, natural capital of the organisation. Integrated reporting is a universal tool that helps to solve the problem of acquiring complete data on the activities of the organisation, both in the perspective of the future and in the past periods.

Human capital management is reflected in management practices. In each of these methods, there are means of structuring the means used and their detailed reflection. The integration of human capital management methods into management reporting will be the most meaningful. Various researchers suggest that human capital should be reflected either from an accounting perspective or as part of sustainability reporting, and suggest that human capital should be viewed from a management perspective and the methods reflected in management reporting [14].

The process of preparing and compiling integrated reporting includes 2 stages: basic and preliminary.

In the main stage of preparing and producing integrated reporting, two key aspects can be identified: methodological and organisational, the importance of which is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Integrated Reporting Process and Preparation Process.

It is necessary at a preliminary stage to:

- explore the similarities and differences between integrated and financial reporting and sustainability reporting;
- summarise the international experience with public reporting.
- Conduct a comparative analysis of the data that are already being generated and those that need to be prepared in order to form an integrated report.

One of the most important features of integrated reporting is that it is not standardised and uniform for all organisations, as it contains qualitative characteristics.

To analyse the state and efficiency of human capital we suggest, by analogy with the analysis of intangible assets, to apply a system of economic indicators that give an idea of the state and dynamics of the object under study. The coefficients of human capital analysis provide an opportunity to get an understanding of the transformation of human capital in dynamics, to identify vulnerable sides, and to prevent complication of the situation. Human capital application efficiency indicators are important for the analysis, as they show the degree of its impact on the financial position of the organisation and its financial results.

To establish the current state and efficiency of the organisation's human capital use, an analysis should be carried out:

- on the level of human capital amortisation;
- the place of human capital in the composition of the organisation's assets;
- human capital dynamics;
- Fund yield and profitability of human capital.

On the level of its amortisation at the 1st stage of the analysis the position of human capital is assessed. During this assessment the coefficients are applied:

- human capital suitability coefficient (C_{hc}). This coefficient reflects the probability of further application, the level of unrecoverable costs of human capital development.

In order to prepare the permanence of successes, it is necessary to preserve and accumulate human capital stocks in the organisation. For this purpose, at the 2nd stage the place of human capital in the composition of the organisation's assets is checked. Coefficients are applied to this case:

- coefficient for determining the specific weight of human capital in the organisation's balance sheet currency (C_{cbhc});
- the coefficient for determining the share of human capital in the composition of long-term assets ($C_{lo.t.as}$);
- the ratio of human capital to fixed assets (C_{fachc}).

At the 3rd stage, the dynamics of changes in the volume of human capital of the organisation for the reporting period is analysed in comparison with the indicators of the base period.

In this case, the following data are used:

- growth rate of the average annual residual value of human capital;
- absolute growth rate of the average annual residual value of human capital;
- the ratio of the growth rate of the average annual residual value of human capital to the growth rate of the balance sheet currency;
- the ratio of the absolute growth rate of human capital to the absolute growth rate of the balance sheet currency.

The analysis of the efficiency of human capital use is characterised by the return, capacity, gross and net profitability of human capital.

At the 4th stage the efficiency of human capital utilisation is analysed, which is determined by such coefficients:

- return on human capital, which is determined by the volume of sales of products, works, services required per 1 UzS of the average annual value of human capital (R_{hc});
- human capital capacity, which determines the need for human capital to produce products, works, services at a cost of 1 UzS (C_{hc});
- gross profitability of human capital, which determines the amount of gross profit required per 1 UzS of human capital (GP_{hc});
- net profitability of human capital, which determines the amount of net profit required per 1 UzS of human capital (NP_{hc}).

The final result of human capital application is shown in the unified results of the organisation's economic activity: reduction of production costs, reduction of product sales, growth of the organisation's solvency and stability of its financial position, and increase in profit.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In the system of management accounting it is predominantly customary to fix cost centres, sales, investments, profit, which in any case relate to the formation of data on the organisation's capitals. In this connection, in order to settle the issue of formation of integrated reporting on human capital, it is possible to fix a special responsibility centre - 'capital centre' in the context of the management accounting system. In the unified system of management accounting the place of this responsibility centre is coordinated with its key purpose, which is to form integrated reporting. The report on human capital of the organisation will be created in the context of integrated reporting.

As a result, the application of the recommended coefficients of the current state and efficiency of human capital application will provide an opportunity to study more deeply the factors that influence the efficiency of its use, to identify growth reserves and to improve forecasting, which will help to make reasoned management decisions.

References

1. Flamholtz E.G. Human Resource Accounting: Advances in Concepts, Methods and Applications the Jossey-Bass management series. - Springer Science & Business Media. - 2012. - 390 p.
2. Валебникова О. А. Необходимость отчетности о процессе управления человеческим капиталом // Сборник трудов всероссийской научной и учебно-практической конференции «Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования в области управления, экономики и торговли». - Санкт-Петербург: Политех-пресс. – 2020. С.132-139.
3. Дипиаза С. А., Эклз Р. Дж. Будущее корпоративной отчетности / Пер. с англ. В. Ионова. – М.: Альпина Паблишер, 2003. – 216 с.
4. Лессидренска Т. Интегрированный отчет – платформа для управления компанией // Экономические стратегии. – 2012. – № 5. – С. 8-9.
5. Легенчук С.Ф. Мировые тенденции развития бухгалтерского учета в условиях постиндустриальной экономики // Международный бухгалтерский учет. – 2011. - № 8. - С. 56 - 62.
6. Малиновская Н.В., Малиновский М.Д. Международные тенденции развития интегрированной отчетности // Международный бухгалтерский учет. - 2018. - Т. 21, № 3. - С. 332 - 343.
7. Самусенко С. А., Харченко Т. О. Сравнительный анализ методов оценки человеческих ресурсов организации // Учет. Анализ. Аудит. - Финансовый университет при Правительстве РФ, Москва. – 2015. - № 4. – С. 23-36.
8. Integrated reporting - IAS Plus. <https://www.iasplus.com/en-gb/resources/integrated-reporting>
9. Герасимов Б.Н., Карпова Т.П. Подпроцесс управления человеческим капиталом: сущность, значимость и место в процессе управления персоналом // Вестник Самарского муниципального института управления. – 2018. - № 4. - С. 112 - 122.
10. Джаншанло Р.Е., Когут О.Ю. Концептуальные основы формирования интегрированной отчетности // Central Asian Economic Review. - Алматы: «АО университет Нархоз», 2020. - № 1(130). - С.111-123.
11. <https://www.ifrs.org/issued-standards/list-of-standards/ias-1-presentation-of-financial-statements.html/content/dam/ifrs/publications/html-standards/english/2024/issued/ias1/20.11.2024>
12. Человеческий капитал: проблемы отражения в учете и отчетности. <https://scienceproblems.ru/chelovecheskij-kapita/2.html> 31.10.2024
13. Когденко В.Г., Мельник М.В. Интегрированная отчетность: вопросы формирования и анализа. Реформирование отчетности // Международный бухгалтерский учет. – 2014. - №10. - С. 2 - 15.
14. Велькер Л. Ю., Чепракова Т. Н. Проблема учета человеческих ресурсов в качестве активов организации // Сборник научных статей 5-ой Всероссийской конференции «Экономический рост как основа устойчивого развития России». – 2020. – С.94-97.

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